

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ORAL KAPOSI'S SARCOMA IN HIV/AIDS PATIENTS: AN UPDATE

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Abstract

Among the manifestations that can appear in patients with HIV/AIDS infection, the lesions of the oral cavity have great relevance because they are easily accessible and generally their diagnosis is made through clinical signs.

Oral manifestations of HIV infections are sometimes the first sign of the infection and often indicate its progression to AIDS.

Some of the oral lesions are ulcerative and painful, which can cause a loss of taste and lead to the loss of dental organs, altering speech, and making chewing and swallowing difficult, which further favors a state of malnutrition, emaciation.

The early lesions are usually flat, asymptomatic, however, together with its evolution, the lesion usually develops a darker red, and asymptomatic.

Kaposi's sarcoma (KS) is an AIDS-defining cancer and was one of the first recognized HIV-related manifestations, appearing in up to 6% of patients.

Palate is the most involved site in oral KS (56%, with 42% for hard palate and 14% for soft palate), but oral KS is also observed on gingiva (22%, with 15% for maxilla and 7% for mandible) and maxillary tuberosity (6%).

Oral KS manifests as purplish macules or nodules that need to be distinguished from other pigmented lesions by histopathological examination.

The massive introduction of anti-retroviral therapy has changed the morbidity and mortality.

The objective of this review is to provide the updated classic clinical characteristics of those oral manifestations associated with HIV/AIDS infection that are more frequent and have greater clinical relevance, considering the fundamental characteristics for their diagnosis.

Keywords: HIV, AIDS, Oral lesions, Kaposi Sarcoma, Dentist.

Introduction

Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) was first acknowledged in 1981 by the American Centers for Disease Control (CDC), and its cause infections were classified in the early part of the decade and the responsible virus was identified as Human Immune Virus (HIV) [1].

HIV attacks vital cells in the human immune system such as helper T cells (specifically CD₄⁺ T cells), macrophages, and dendritic cells and this will eventually lead to low levels of CD₄⁺ and T cells rendering loss of mediated immunity [2,3].

Among the manifestations that can appear in patients with HIV/AIDS infection, the lesions of the oral cavity are of great relevance [4]. Studies carried out around the world indicate that these lesions can be existent in up to 50% of persons with HIV infection and in 80% of individuals diagnosed with AIDS [5]. The differences in percentage are due to the variety of investigations, methodologies, study types, epidemiological heterogeneity, demographic region and type of therapy the patient is receiving [6].

The risk of emerging opportunistic infections and tumors typical of AIDS as Kaposi's sarcoma, lymphoma, increases progressively as CD4 counts fall below 200 cells/mm³ [7-9].

The presence of oral lesions continues to be significant since it could be indicative of a deterioration of the patient's immune system, considering them as early

markers of the disease [4]. They can also be associated with a decrease in the count of CD4 T lymphocytes and an increase in the viral load [5].

In the context of a patient with HIV infection/AIDS, the importance of oral lesions lies mainly in the fact that: they are easily accessible and generally their diagnosis is carried out through clinical signs and some oral manifestations are strongly related to HIV/AIDS because of what they indicate suspected infection [10].

In the eighties, a classification of the oral manifestations associated with HIV/AIDS infection in adult patients was proposed based on the degree of association or frequency of said pathological conditions with the presence of the virus [11].

In 2009, this classification was revised and updated by experts grouped in OHARA (Oral HIV/AIDS Research Alliance) with the objective of facilitating the diagnosis of these lesions to carry out clinical studies and epidemiological [12, 13].

There are about 40 described oral manifestations of AIDS related to the classification of the European Economic Community [12-15]. Oral manifestations of HIV infections could be occasionally the first signal of the infection and habitually signify its progression to AIDS [15]. HIV infected patients regularly involve a variety of opportunistic infections because of reduced cellular immune activity, leading to oral lesions

such as candidiasis, reactivation of Herpes Simplex Virus (HSV), and Cytomegalovirus (CMV)- related ulcerations [14, 16].

The presence of oral lesions associated with HIV/AIDS has a great impact on the quality of life of these patients some are ulcerative and painful, which can trigger a loss of taste and lead to the loss of dental organs, varying speech, and making chewing and swallowing difficult, which further favors a state of malnutrition, emaciation [5, 10, 17].

The natural progress of HIV infection has swapped particularly as a result of the introduction of highly active anti-retroviral therapy (HAART), which was first dispensed IN 1999 [18].

In 2013, the World Health Organization (WHO) has suggested a combination of antiretroviral drugs for treating and prevention of HIV infection [19].

However, the occurrence of some lesions classically associated with HIV infection such as Kaposi's sarcoma, hairy leukoplakia, periodontal disease and ulcerations of the mucosa have decreased with the introduction of HAART, other conditions such as oropharyngeal candidiasis, have remained constant, while papillomatous lesions and salivary gland pathology have increased [20].

The purpose of this paper is to present an update of oral Kaposi's sarcoma associated with HIV/AIDS and stress the role of dentist in having greater clinical relevance, considering the fundamental characteristics for their diagnosis the diagnosis.

Kaposi Sarcoma

Kaposi's sarcoma (KS) is an AIDS-defining tumor and was one of the first acknowledged HIV-related manifestations, emerging in up to 6% of patients, and has been particularly decreasing due to the use of HAART [21, 22].

It is an Angio proliferative, multicentric disease of endothelial origin, with pathogenesis and a quite heterogeneous clinical expression and a type of growth that is directly related to the immune response of the host [23]. Start as a reactive hyperplastic anti-inflammatory reaction and an angiogenic process that evolves into a sarcoma [24].

In 1981, the most common and aggressive variant of KS was first reported among homosexual men [25].

HIV-related KS in Africa occurs in males and females similarly [26], and the incidence is amplified by 20-fold in Africa and in the United States [27,28].

KS may appear in any part of the body like a visible purplish-black patches, or lesions, on skin, mucous membranes containing oral ones, or internal organs. KS is detected at all stages of HIV infection, but it is mostly serious when CD4 cell count falls below 200 [22, 23].

Patients with depress CD4 counts will more likely grow KS in internal organs, such as lungs and lymph nodes, with possible life-threatening sequelae [23].

Etiology

KS is triggered by Human Herpes Virus 8 (HHV-8), recognized also as KS associated Herpes Virus (KSHV) which infects endothelial and B cells [29]

This virus is acknowledged to be mainly sexually transmitted, specifically within homosexual society [25].

Existing data indicates the presence and extensive expression of HHV-8 virus in the oral mucosa and saliva, making it one of the fundamental sites for viral duplication and shedding of the virus [30].

The incidence of HHV-8 is indispensable for development of KS and its existing in all KS cells [31].

The diminished immunity and the infection with HIV-1 play an important responsibility in emerging the disease when complemented with HHV-8 [29].

Clinical appearance

OKS appear as nodular, macular, raised, or ulcerated with a color variety from red to purple. but early lesions generally present red, asymptomatic, and flat, whereas older ones are darker color [32-34].

However, together with its evolution, the lesion usually develops dark color with convergent lesions [34].

Palate is the utmost involved site in OKS (56%) with 42% for hard palate and 14% for soft palate), but also is observed on gingiva (22%), with 15% for maxilla and 7% for mandible and maxillary tuberosity (6%) [33-35].

The convincing diagnosis of this tumors is completed according to clinical characteristics and diagnosis requires histopathological analysis after performing a biopsy [36].

Initially, the lesions tend to be flat and asymptomatic, where the color transits from red to purple [32-35].

They can also present as irregular volume increases, of a vinous red color, which when they reach a considerable size can cause facial deformity and alterations in chewing, swallowing and can ulcerate due to chewing trauma, be painful and can even bleed against stimuli [32-35]. In almost one fifth of HIV-infected patients, OKS is the first manifestation of the disease [34]. Additionally, OKS can be the initial indicator of HIV infection [36].

Treatment

Various treatment strategies for OKS are recommended in the literature, dependent on the type and severity of the disease and it is important to assess for systemic involvements prior to the start of the treatment [37].

Treatment options comprise observation, local approaches and systemic therapy. In cases of limited asymptomatic lesions, no intervention is required [20, 24, 32, 37].

While local approaches are expended for focal or extensive regional lesions, systemic therapy is reserved for cases with systemic involvements [37-42]

Local methods vary from excision, sclerotherapy, intra-lesion injection with vinca alkaloids, photodynamic therapy, radiotherapy and cryotherapy [40].

Systemic approaches incorporate, but are not limited to HAART, chemotherapy, sirolimus, anti-HHV-8 agents, in addition to other medications [38, 40-42].

Radiotherapy is kept for symptomatic and obstructive oropharyngeal KS [40,43].

After the introduction of HAART, the prevalence as well as the severity of OKS has reduced [37,38,40,42].

Although HIV-associated KS is the most common form cases have been reported in HIV-seronegative patients [44].

Although cutaneous lesions were reported most of the above-mentioned cases had oral manifestations without any other mucosal, cutaneous or lymphatic involvements [45].

Conclusion

Knowledge of the different clinical presentations, symptoms and behavior of oral lesions is essential to make a timely diagnosis and treatment in patients with HIV/AIDS infection, as well as make a diagnostic suspicion in case of unknown immunosuppressive disease.

However, we need to consider that the most important thing is to know the clinical characteristics of the different oral manifestations associated with HIV/AIDS infection has to do with the unification of diagnostic criteria that allow us to know the frequency of these lesions in the HIV/AIDS population. This would contribute to the development of public health policies, with a strong epidemiological basis.

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Figure legends

Figure 1: Kaposi's Sarcoma lesion in the skin of HIV patient.

Figure 2: OKS lesion in the gingiva as nodular lesion with a color variety from red to purple.

Figure 3: OKS generalized tumefaction lesions in the attached gingiva with dark color.

Figure 4: OKS localized tumefaction in the retro-molar area with pink and purple color and affecting the chewing process.

Figure 5: a- OKS flat and asymptomatic and the color is red in the soft palate.

b- OKS diffuse flat and asymptomatic and the color is red in the complete palate.

Figure 6: a- OKS tumoral in the hard palate attached to the gingiva with ulceration and very dark color.

b- OKS tumoral in the hard palate in the attached gingiva and very dark color and the tumor are very diffuse.

Figures.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5: a and b.

Figure 6: a and b.